

Socio-Psychological Directions of Resocialization of Persons, Who are Located in Places of Imprisonment

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Abstract: *The psycho-pedagogical and social rehabilitation of individuals before dismissal from the places of imprisonment is currently relevant, as it is a qualitative return to normal life that becomes an acute problem for people who are preparing to leave the places of imprisonment. The purpose of the article is to analyze the pilot psychological and pedagogical research of persons who are in places of imprisonment. For introduction of the developed social-pedagogical directions of resocialization of persons who are in the places of detention or getting ready to leave these places, the diagnostics of psychological characteristics which will become key signs of efficiency of the applied directions became relevant, namely: orientation to changing of the social environment; social-pedagogical therapy; professional orientation during teaching and educational process. Diagnostics of structure of intelligence, educational motivation, nonverbal creativity and level of self-assessment of persons who are in places of detention is performed. The analysis of results of motives of educational activity allows saying that educational activity of respondents is defined by motivation on achievement, cognitive motivation, and by motive of external stimulation. The highest indicator of the index of uniqueness that characterizes nonverbal creativity is met at most of respondents. The self-assured personality is guided by development of the his/her potential, he/she subordinates the existence to achievement of a condition of integrity, integration, spontaneity, humour, openness of experience. Creative, motivated, intelligently flexible and self-assured personality can achieve the objectives, far from creativity, for the sake of prospects in his/her life. He/she can be attracted to the activity necessary from some reasons, important for him/her, as, for example, participation of creative people in technical activity, in organizational work, for explanation of his/her purposes for other people.*

Keywords: *educational motivation; nonverbal creativity; self-assessment; structure of intelligence.*

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1. Introduction

The psycho-pedagogical and social rehabilitation of individuals before dismissal from the places of imprisonment is currently relevant, as it is a qualitative return to normal life that becomes an acute problem for people who are preparing to leave the places of imprisonment.

Recognized to be innovative the sphere of providing social-pedagogical services to persons released from places of imprisonment, requires further structural and organizational registration and legislative regulation. Resolving the issue of effective preparation of prisoners for releasing is one of the key tasks of penitentiary and post penitentiary theory and practice. For convicts who have served their sentence for a long time, and have lost socially useful connections and, for the most part, do not have a place for living, a profession and even a proper education, adaptation to life in freedom in modern conditions is very complicated. Their successful social, psychological and pedagogical adaptation is one of the priority directions of state policy, since the difficulties in restoring their social status and returning to normal living conditions lead to the fact that those who have been released from penitentiary institutions are returning to the criminal way, because of which the level of relapse of crimes is increasing.

There is practically complete lacking of the necessary number of trained social pedagogues-practitioners, psychologists, subject teachers which are able to work with different categories of convicts in a new way. The studies of psychological and pedagogical indicators, the analysis of the results of which will help to orient the specialists in choosing, developing, modifying the correct and effective psycho-pedagogical and social innovative technologies for the re-socialization of persons in detention are in the same deficit.

Psycho-pedagogical and social work with convicts is by itself a multidisciplinary type of activity. One of the most important directions of activity of social and pedagogical work with convicts is their personal preparation for release from places of imprisonment and social-pedagogical and psychological work with their families, which became the object of research of M. Denysova (2010), V. Druzhinin (2007), A. Kapska (2017), A. Makarenko (1997), V. Nalyvaiko (2000), A. Stepaniuk (2015). Employees of correctional colonies (prisons) interact in solving issues of labor and household assistance to those persons which are being released from places of imprisonment. This is primarily assistance in the spheres of care, healthcare, education, social protection of the population, work with the Commission on Juvenile Affairs and the protection of their rights. All these

types of social-pedagogical work are necessary and traditional, which need modern improvement and create conditions for our further research.

The purpose of the article is to analyze the pilot psychological and pedagogical research of persons who are in places of imprisonment.

2. Materials and Methods

Among the specially developed educational forms and technologies successfully implemented in our country, the following have proved to be effective: the use of psychological and pedagogical training using the methods of persuasion and suggestion; organization of work of rooms of relaxation; involving convicts in various forms of creative activity of humanistic orientation; purposeful work on the selection, formation and training of the assets of convicts, the wider use of the elements of self-government on the basis of involving the assets of convicted persons in the planning, preparation and implementation of educational activities, organization of pedagogically appropriate leisure; interaction of employees of various parts and services with the public, in particular with representatives of different religious denominations.

Under the resourcefulness of educational work, it is necessary to understand not only the availability of funds, technical means, and, above all, the staffing of institutions with highly skilled professional staff capable of implementing and realization of programs for the education and rehabilitation of convicts.

Thus, it is worth emphasizing the importance of the formation of positive interpersonal relations among convicts, which originate directly from the environmental conditionality of the correction of the personality of the prisoner who does not independently choose an environment. The forced stay in the department designated by the administration dramatically increases the value of the immediate social environment (micro-environment).

It is very difficult to form positive interpersonal relationships among prisoners, but it is extremely necessary.

The above principle is closely linked with the following - the principle of adherence to the rule of law in the process of re-socialization.

The peculiarity of the pedagogical process in places of imprisonment is its dependence on legal regulations, the necessity of subordination of educational actions to the requirements of the legal norms of criminal-executive law, which regulate the relationship between the object and subject, educational influence, determine the main means of re-socialization and legal requirements for their implementation. specifies the specifics of

educational work, security and law and order, general and vocational education in the conditions of penitentiary institutions, the involvement of convicts in different types of labor activity, the legal aspects of the application of pedagogical methods and techniques, in particular means of encouragement and punishment are substantiated.

Educators, social workers involved in working with prisoners must fully and deeply understand the norms of the criminal-executive and other branches of law and strictly adhere to them in practice.

Of course, it should be emphasized that not always the existing legal norms regulating the activity of investigative isolation units are fully pedagogically expedient. But this is another aspect of the problem – it is necessary to scientifically substantiate the legal norms, which are accepted at the legislative level, taking into account the laws of psychology and pedagogy. And the officially accepted norm of the law should be mandatory for the activities and behavior of all – both convicted and those involved in working with them.

Correction of a minor naturally depends on the peculiarities of various types of his activity and those relations that arise in its process.

In some pedagogical concepts of the past, the idea of verbal education prevailed: the educator influenced the upbringing only by means of explanation, persuasion, exhortation, etc.

Warning about the harm of only verbal education, A. Makarenko (1997) repeatedly emphasized that consciousness is formed as a result of activity, that there is a “small groove” between consciousness and action, which must be filled with experience (p. 206).

Only activity puts the pupil in an active position relative to the surrounding reality, includes it in a variety of upbringing relationships. In investigative isolators, in conditions of isolation, sensory deficits, the creative activity of the personality acquires a special significance.

It is worth reminding that, in addition to the labor and production activities, the concept of activity includes both educational and public, as well as communication and game. This should be especially taken into account in work with convicted of young age groups.

From the specified pattern the following pedagogical principles follow:

- re-education of convicts is carried out in various types of their activities, forming a system of socially meaningful relationships with reality;
- the principle of unity of social value of activity and its subjective significance for convicts. This means that convicted person is being raised the most by such activity, which fully takes into account his personal

interests, provides activity and allows him to optimally demonstrate his abilities.

The effectiveness of the re-socialization of the convicted persons naturally depends on the correspondence of content, forms and methods of educational impact on the personality as a holistic psychological phenomenon, in particular the attitude of the convicted person to the crime and the criminal punishment for it.

Practice shows that in the case when the convict considers himself completely innocent of the crime, does not feel repentance, and to the extent of criminal punishment is regarded as unfair, then, naturally, there is a negative attitude to pedagogical influence. Correction of such and other prisoners can only be successful if we manage to form at them feelings of guilty for the crimes committed, repentance, the attitude towards punishment as fair, and to the profession of a prison officer as important, necessary and socially significant.

It is also worth noting that each person is unique, for every juvenile one has to find his “key” and try to penetrate into the underlying interior of his inner world.

In order to achieve a positive result, taking into account the above-mentioned regularities, it is necessary to adhere to such principles as individual and differentiated approach to minors, an integrated approach to re-education, a combination of strictness of prisoners with respect for their personality, and humane and just attitude towards them.

The principle of an individual and differentiated approach means taking into account in the educational work the individual features of convicts, as well as features common to their various categories. The concept of “subordinates”, “convicted” from psychological, demographic and other positions is very diverse. They can be differentiated according to the age, orientation of the personality, the nature of the crimes committed, the number of convictions, the degree of pedagogical neglect, the informal position in their community (“trump card”, “angular”, “torpedo”, “six”, etc.).

Differentiation of the prosecuted and convicted persons can become a unique tool in the hands of the investigator of detention center, which enables to optimally develop and implement “typical” programs of educational work with different categories of convicts, most accurately and subtly to find approaches to the personality as a unique individuality, and on this basis to specify such programs.

The principle of a comprehensive approach to re-education involves understanding the person as a holistic psychological phenomenon and

means the need to study, develop and correct its intellectual, emotional-volitional, value-orientation spheres, and behavior. These tasks are realized by the means of mental, moral, labor, legal, physical, valeological, aesthetic and other interrelated directions of the educational process in their unity and interdependence.

A comprehensive approach requires the rational use of the entire range of forms, content, methods and means of upbringing, foresees the coherence and continuity of the actions of all subjects of the educational process, aimed at the re-socialization of convicts at different stages of serving the sentence, taking into account the dynamics of personal changes in consciousness and behavior of convicts throughout the process of re-education in places of detention and after release.

In the principle of combination of strictness to convicted persons with respect for personality, humane and just attitude to them the dialectic of the educational process reflects, which is complicated by the specifics of being in the detention center.

To be humane for the convicts means to believe in the possibility of their correction, to pass this faith to themselves. To do this, one must be able to set reasonable and fair demands, as well as create conditions where compliance with them leads not to thoughtless obedience, but to conscious discipline, to the formation of readiness to work on himself. Humanity and strictness are organically interconnected and form two sides of the same principle. For its proper implementation, investigative detention officers should be careful about prisoners, while avoiding the two extremes: on the one hand, it is a substitution for the strictness by administration, roughness, abuse, disciplinary punishment, and, on the other, a manifestation of a false sense of pity for criminals, connivance, flirting with them.

Requirements for convicts must be purposeful and realistic, have a certain structure, and are based on the basic criteria of socio-pedagogical work, according to which psycho-corrective effects on the convict will be carried out. (Nedybalyuk, 2013, p. 169.)

It should be borne in mind, however, that the low requirements (first of all, this applies to representatives of the council of assets of convicts) can lead to the “decay” of the asset, unhealthy relations between the convicts, undermining the authority of employees.

The requirements to the personality of the convicted person, taking into account the dynamics of his correction, should not be weakened, but at the same time it is important to diversify their forms and techniques, using both direct (order, prohibition, command) and indirect claims (hint, warning of inevitable consequences and etc.). The requirements of educators should

be supplemented, and sometimes consistently replaced by the requirements of the team, the group to the convict and the demands of the convict to himself. The humanity of the employees of the investigative detention center is incompatible with the brutality and with suppression of the human dignity of the convicted person. Every convicted person should be seen as a citizen of a society, which has, though limited, but established by law rights and obligations.

The effectiveness of the correction of the convict objectively depends on his own active self-education activities.

In recent years, new effective means of individual and group influence on convicts are constantly being implemented in the work of modern penitentiary institutions. However, only external conditions and actions concerning the personality can not ensure its development and correction, because their influence is mediated by the internal world of the convict, his views, his attitude to the surrounding reality, his personal activity.

Many years of practice show that the implementation of any number of educational activities will not produce the desired results if the prisoners themselves do not want to carefully examine the peculiarities of their character, critically treat themselves and consciously, systematically engage in self-education, restoration, formation and development of positive traits, habits and so on.

The effectiveness of educational work in institutions of execution of sentences is determined by many factors, but they all act on the convicted person only through his activity, his attitude to all influences. In other words, a convicted person should become not only an object but also a subject of educational influences.

It is difficult to achieve a result if the convict does not see expediency in changing the features of his character, or does not believe in the possibility of correction. Consequently, from the above-mentioned regularity, the principle of stimulation and pedagogical leadership of the self-education of convicts follows. Its realization is connected with the help for the convict to understand objectively his personality, to critically analyze the drawbacks and to define the saved positive features, with the motivation of him to work on himself and study methods and techniques of influence on himself.

Overcoming the negative qualities of the personality of the convict is naturally associated with the approach to it with an optimistic hypothesis, based on positive features and qualities.

Sometimes all individual work with prisoners is directed only to fight his drawbacks. If the results can not be reached immediately, they say: "This person can not be re-educated." Such mood is passed to a convict, he loses his faith in himself, and isn't eager to work on himself. Ignoring the above-mentioned regularity can nullify all the efforts of the staff of the investigative detention center.

Taking this pattern into account, it is necessary in the penitentiary activity to consistently implement the principles of supporting the educational work on positive qualities, preserved social relations and personal relations, forecasting, identifying, forming and developing this positive.

This principle reflects the most important psycho-pedagogical position, which emphasizes the need to take into account the needs of people in self-declaration and self-affirmation. The practice shows that the positive in the personality of a prisoner can be revealed in the features of his behavior associated with such a biopsychic property as balance, stability of the type of the nervous system (temperament), or, for example, in mature intellectual development, subtlety of emotional and sensual, or force of the volitional sphere (which is a substructure of mental processes). Positive in the personality of the convict in many cases can be found in the development, preserving of his social experience, professional and general cultural knowledge, skills and habits, useful habits (at least, for example, sanitary-hygienic content).

Experienced employees of the investigative detention center are well aware that even with the general negative attitudes of criminals and in this substructure of personality, many of them have positive features associated with the development of social interests and inclinations, the presence of positive ideals in general, the preservation of civic convictions that characterize understanding and the personal acceptance by prisoners of such, for example, social values, as patriotism, mercy, justice, etc.

It is known that one of the most important for the re-education of personality attitudes is the attitude towards oneself, his behavior, and hence to his crime, his past and future. If in this sphere of personality the penitentiary worker can identify such positive features as self-criticism or worry about the crime committed on the basis of true repentance, one can rely on the reality of achieving the goal of returning to a society of a law-abiding person.

The most important field of finding the positive in the personality and supporting him – the abilities of the prisoner: organizing, professionally working, sports, creative, etc.

There is a very important pedagogical tool – an opportunity to give a person a "do-it-yourself" (a kind of work or social activity, creative leisure activities), to give him/her a chance to positively show him/herself, earn other people's appreciation, or simply enjoy the success, "inner encouragement "

It is also necessary to carefully and diligently identify the positive aspects in the social relationships of the prisoner: maintaining a happy relationship in the family, the group where he previously worked or studied, the informal groups he was a member of (circle of communication with friends, creative, self-employed, sports and other associations, groups and sections); obtaining a high social status in the system of informal interpersonal relationships with other prisoners.

It is worth emphasizing that none of the above regularities works in itself, all the established regularities and principles form a single interacting system.

The pilot psychological and pedagogical research was conducted by the Department of Social Work of PHEI "Kropyvnytskyi Institute of State and Municipal Management". The respondents were pupils of evening school №38 – people who are in the places of imprisonment in Kropyvnytskyi city, there were 30 of them, aged from 16 to 47 years old. The study was conducted in November 2018.

To study the structure of intelligence, self-esteem, creativity and motivational characteristics of the personality who are preparing to leave the places of imprisonment, the following methodologies were used:

- Methodology "Diagnostics of the structure of educational motivation" by M. Fetiskin (Fetiskin et al., 2005);

- Methodology "Diagnostics of non-verbal creativity (shortened version of the test of P. Torrens)" by A. Voronin (Druzhinin, 2007);

- "Method of diagnostics of the structure of intelligence", the test of R. Amthauer (shortened version developed by A. Voronin and S. Biryukov) (Druzhinin, 2007);

- Methodology "Verbal diagnostics of self-esteem of the personality" by M. Fetiskin (Fetiskin et al., 2005).

3. Results

Social-pedagogical work with convicts is a multidisciplinary type of activity by itself. One of the most important directions of activity of social and pedagogical work with convicts is their personal preparation for release from places of imprisonment, which is aimed at the resocialization of the prisoners themselves. The main purpose of re-socialization is to return to

the society a "socially healthy" person capable of intellectual self-improvement, revealing of creative abilities, positive motivation for a qualitative professional and everyday life, with an adequate self-esteem; prepared for different living conditions that exist in society.

To investigate creativity, the method of diagnostics of non-verbal creativity is used, which represents the 12 subtests proposed by P. Torrens. One of the subtests "Completion of pictures." was used in the study. When using this test, special emphasis was placed on identifying non-verbal creativity as a certain ability to create a new, original product under minimal verbalization. In other words – the verbalization of the material with which the subject is working and the means of creating a new product is not necessary and secondary. With this test, we determined the level of originality and the level of uniqueness.

After questioning a group of 30 respondents, we determined that the level of non-verbal creativity of the investigated prisoners (according to the index of originality) is below the average (18%). However, for its evaluation the index of uniqueness is more important: the result of the index of uniqueness (72%) suggests that the creation of a unique product of activity is possible for all respondents. The uniqueness of this category of people has high rates, indicating that there are remarkable creative abilities in the investigated personalities.

Self-confident personality focuses on the development of its potential, it submits its existence to the achievement of the state of integrity, integrity, spontaneity, humor, openness of experience. The creative person can achieve far from creativeness goals for the sake of the prospects in his life; he/she can be involved in activities necessary for some important reasons for him/her, such as the participation of creative people in technical activities, in organizational work, for explanation their goals to other people, etc. At a high level of creativity, confident in his/her strength and abilities, the person thoroughly approaches the tasks, faster and more qualitatively reaches the ultimate goal of cognitive activity and has a creative level of the latter.

Methodology "Diagnostics of the structure of *educational motivation*" allowed to study the most significant motives of educational activity and their qualitative analysis in people of all ages. Educational motivation is an appropriate indicator for professional self-determination and can be taken into account when getting education for people preparing for leaving places of imprisonment.

The motive of the educational process is the driving force behind the process of vocational training. The motive for learning is the internal

motive force that provides the movement of the personality to cognitive activity, activates intellectual development in the process of activity. In the role of motives may be the needs and interests, aspirations and emotions, settings and ideals. From the psychological point of view, motives are the internal motive of educational activity, which determines the success and effectiveness of the latter.

In our study, we identified several group motives for learning activities. We indicate in percents the quantitative characteristics of each motive at respondents.

Cognitive motive (46%) - appears in the awakening of cognitive interests and is realized through the satisfaction of the process of cognition and its results. Cognitive activity of a person is the leading sphere of his/her life. Therefore, the formation of cognitive motifs in people is a leading factor in the success of cognitive activity, because through him the natural need of a person is realized. This is connected with the fact that evening school teachers adapt the teaching material from each discipline and use it according to the age-specific characteristics and intellectual abilities of each student.

Communicative motive is expressed in the desire for communication. Like the need for activities, a person needs communication, the satisfaction of which is a necessary condition for normal mental and social development of personality and development of cognitive activity (39%).

The motive for emotional satisfaction is the interest in a certain type of activity, the process of fulfilling this action, a positive emotional state during the educational activity, a sense of joy and satisfaction with learning (33%).

The motive for self-development is the understanding of the importance of knowledge, the need for self-education, the dissatisfaction with the level of their knowledge, the desire and the wish to independently solve the problem, despite the fact that people are in places of imprisonment (34%).

External stimulation – the desire to earn approval from comrades, the collective, the manifestation of selfishness and ambition, fear of a teacher (45%).

The motive of achievement – the desire to be an educated member of society, responsibility, duty to the team, society, parents, the benefit of mastering the future profession, mercantile, material benefits, rapid career. For 58% of the respondents, the dominance of the motive of achievement is outstanding, and this is especially clearly seen in educational activities.

Compared with other motifs, the motive of achievement is of the greatest importance in the educational activities of all the investigated. We assume that many of the respondents are guided by certain future creative achievements, success in their careers, and avoiding problems in finding employment, which depends on their current success in learning activities. This gives an opportunity to make a qualitative interpretation of the fact that the main motivation for the respondents is internal, including the motivation of the achievement.

By means of the method of diagnostics of *the structure of intelligence* there were attempts to study the level of general intellectual abilities, the main group factors of the structure of intelligence and their qualitative analysis among respondents of different ages. The test diagnoses the general intelligence (G - factor by Spirman) and its main group factors, namely: spatial, numeric and verbal. The so-called "G-factor" is the general ability to study. The mark is obtained based on the compilation of indicators of three factors: verbal, numeric, and three-dimensional space perception testing. The total score for all factors determines the overall assessment of the level of intelligence.

Unfortunately, out of 30 respondents, only 25% at least tried to answer the test questions. Only 1 respondent answered 16 questions of the test, giving correct answers.

Analyzing the results of the respondents' responses, it was found that the calculation-mathematical vector, that is, the numerical part of the test has suffered the greatest difficulties. Only 13% of respondents answered one question of this block. Three correct answers were given to the blocks for the study of spatial thinking and memory and concentration of attention.

The analysis of the results of the diagnosis of the level of general intelligence revealed that the level of its indicators is determined predominantly by the experience of the subject of education and training in interaction with the surrounding society, the success and level of knowledge received, etc.

Using the method of verbal diagnosis of *personality self-assessment*, the following self-esteem indicators of respondents of different age groups were determined.

The analysis of indicators shows that the overwhelming majority of the examined – 70% (the average score of self-esteem level is 44) has an average level self-esteem (respondents aged from 26 to 35 years old). Only 15% of the respondents have a high level (respondents aged from 14 to 25 years old) and one has a low level (two respondents aged 47 and one aged 36 years old).

The data show that most of the people surveyed are people who rarely suffer from infertility, trying to adjust to the opinion of other people from time to time. Respondents with high self-esteem are self-confident, responsive to comments, and rarely doubt the need for their actions. 3% of respondents are painfully tolerant of critical remarks, they are not self-assured. But let us note that, unlike other qualities of a personality, self-esteem is quite variable and in many cases depends on the situation, conditions and period of life, events.

4. Discussion and conclusions

Psychological and pedagogical aspects of the problem of humanizing the socializing process in places of imprisonment are connected, first of all, with the implementation to the practice the productive ideas of cooperation pedagogy.

Pedagogy of cooperation is defined as a progressive concept that establishes a special style of dialogic communication between teachers and students, aimed at creating in the object of education the position of an active, conscious subject of personally significant and socially useful activities (Yanova, 2020, p. 1). The main value components of cooperation pedagogy that can be considered as professional settings of the educator, which are essential for the implementation of this progressive concept, include the following:

- 1) an optimistic forecast in assessing the prospects of personality changes of a person in detention;
- 2) the acceptance (and not rejection) of every adolescent, boy or adult "as he is", with all his disadvantages, contradictions, etc., as well as the respectful attention to the person;
- 3) empathetic (and not only appreciated) sympathetic understanding of the personality of the prisoner, taking into account the complexity of his mental states;
- 4) providing the prisoner with the social-psychological and other assistance necessary for him to overcome the difficulties in various spheres of life (of course, within the law), to create and consolidate a psychotherapeutic (or, at the least, non-psychotropic) climate of the environment where he is in;
- 5) the search for positive aspects in the person who is in places of imprisonment for the use of these positive aspects in the pedagogical process;
- 6) in-depth study and disclosure of the actual motives and external circumstances that determine the behaviour and actions of the individual,

taking into account his/her characteristics, the main needs, mental states and the adoption of optimal, concrete individualized solutions on this basis;

7) activation of consciousness and self-consciousness of law-breakers with appeal to their intellectual powers and development of the latter;

8) critical introspection, correction by an employee of the institution, social worker of his own personality and pedagogical activity for the purpose of self-improvement (Soloviev, 2012, p. 3).

By organizing the process of re-socialization of the individual in conditions of imprisonment, it is necessary to understand his essence, the basic laws inherent in this process, and the principles of its implementation.

Knowledge of the regularities and principles of the pedagogical process in the conditions of imprisonment is necessary for employees to get deeper into the essence of the correction of the person of the prisoner, to ensure the scientific principles of management of this process. Deep knowledge of the laws and principles of the pedagogical process helps to determine the most effective forms and methods of influencing the consciousness, feelings and behavior of prisoners.

The regularities of the pedagogical process are reflected in the basic principles of penitentiary pedagogy regarding the resocialization of those who committed the crime. Penitentiary pedagogy does not reduce the principles of re-socialization to the sum of some specific recipes and rules, but treats them as a set of guiding ideas, requirements for the implementation of social-pedagogical process in prison.

Principles of resocialization of the person, who is in places of imprisonment, are the leading key ideas arising from the regularities, essence and peculiarities of the process of resocialization.

It should be emphasized that these principles derive from the essence of the goals of re-education and are conditioned by the nature of the social system, the objectivity of pedagogical laws, the peculiarity and specificity of the pedagogical process in the penitentiary institutions. The specificity of the principles is also due to the peculiarities of the prisoner's personality.

It must be understood that the force of objective laws is that they operate in a society irrespective of our wishes or prohibitions, decisions of sessions, congresses or meetings of departmental boards. Nobody can abolish the laws, it is an objectively existing reality.

It is known that the system of education is determined the social structure of society, its spiritual culture. This is reflected in the definition of

goals and objectives, the social ideal of the individual, the model of those features and qualities that should be formed at the pupils.

The development of social relations naturally left its imprint on the actually progressive for its time Pennsylvanian system of punishment of the eighteenth century (in single cells of prisons the criminals were alone with themselves and the Bible, in complete silence and isolation from the outside world, which often led to suicide, loss mental equilibrium), and on the Oberon system of punishment of the nineteenth century (convicts were categorically forbidden to speak among themselves, they could apply to the administration only in extreme cases and only by whisper or using facial expressions and gestures). These systems have helped to completely restrict convicts from any involvement in solving their own destiny or even insignificant improvements in their state.

Totalitarian society has their own ideals, idols, ideas (denial of universal values in favor of mythical class morality), their own slogans ("The goal justifies the means"), which, of course, reflected on the goals and objectives of the re-socialization of the convicts. The level of social relations naturally predetermined the task of penitentiary institutions – the formation of an obedient, fanatically devoted to the communist idea of "cog" of the state machine (Soloviev, 2012, p. 93).

It becomes clear why in the 30-ies of the 20th century in our penitentiary institutions humanistic ideas and methodical advice of the outstanding teacher, the head of the Poltava and the Kuryag colonies, and then the deputy head of the labor colonies of the NKVS of Ukraine A. Makarenko (1997) (the combination of respect and demanding to the personality of the convicted person, the protection of him/her in the team, the system of responsible dependence as prevention of the "decay" of the active core, hypertrophy of the functions of self-government, etc.). The objectives and content of the system of A. Makarenko significantly outstripped the level of social relations at that time (Makarenko, 1997, p. 237).

In the period of development of an independent democratic constitutional state the ideas of humanism, pedagogy of cooperation and respect for a person are naturally highlighted.

On the basis of the consideration of the logical connection between the nature of social relations and the purpose, tasks, content of the pedagogical process in the practice of the staff of the penitentiary institutions, the principles that determine the main directions of work with the lawbreakers must be realized. This is, first of all, the principle of

purposefulness of the pedagogical process for the resocialization of young people.

The objective basis of optimism in assessing the possibilities of correction of the convicted person is the doctrine of plasticity of the nervous system and the possibility of reorganizing a dynamic stereotype, of the leading role of social factors (primarily, targeted educational activities, including self-education) in the formation and correction of the personality.

The next principle that follows from the mentioned laws is the close connection of the process of re-socialization with real life. In the detention center, this principle becomes of particular importance as a result of certain physical isolation and limited social status of a minor.

An analysis of the thoughts of social workers, teachers, educators, and psychologists, personal observations of authors and interviews of individuals who are in prison, suggests that many of them are very poorly oriented in the problems of modern life, in the difficulties with which they can encounter in everyday life after being released.

On implementing the principle of close connection of the process of re-socialization with real life, it is envisaged to renew and establish socially useful connections and relationships of prisoners, to constantly familiarize them with social-economic, political problems, to form positive social attitudes, to involve them in social useful and personally significant activity. To do this you need to use a variety of media; attract prisoners to read newspapers, magazines, listening to radio broadcasts, etc., with appropriate pedagogically expedient interpretation of the information provided.

The effectiveness of re-socialization naturally depends on the quality of educational work and its resourcefulness, from the social environment (external and internal) of specific institutions (Sitkovskaya, 1998, p. 55).

A comprehensive analysis of the results of the study on the above-mentioned methods suggests as the existence of similarities (approximately the same, by the values, level of general intelligence), but also some differences between respondents of different ages. For example, the predominant lack of performance of the subtest for the numerical factor in the structure of intelligence is the most common among respondents, which suggests a low level of intelligence structure, while the analysis of the subtest indicators for the verbal factor survey showed a high value only in 16% of respondents. Analysis of the results of the motives of educational activities suggests that the educational activity of the respondents is determined by the motivation for achievement, cognitive motivation, and the motivation of external stimulation. The highest indicator of the uniqueness index characterizing the component of "creativity" occurs in

most of the respondents, while the index of originality is only 18% of the respondents.

Preparation of convicts for leaving the places of imprisonment is based on the diligent work in the system of measures for the preliminary solution of issues of social-psychological and intellectual development, labor and domestic sets of convicts, which foresee their pedagogical, psychological, ethical, legal preparation, effective provision of direct assistance in restoration and the development of socially useful ties between convicts.

The next step in our study will be the introduction of developed social-pedagogical directions of re-socialization of persons preparing for leaving the places of imprisonment, namely: orientation towards changing social environment; social psychological therapy; professional orientation during the educational process.

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